

Editorial Workflows in Diamond Open Access Journals: A Guide

Authors:

Iryna Kuchma, EIFL

Ina Smith, Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf)

Milica Ševkušić, EIFL

June 2026

This work is licensed under a
[Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Introduction

This guide is designed to help Diamond Open Access (OA) journals (those that charge no fees, either for readers or authors) establish and manage editorial workflows. The guide can be used for managing journals through a dedicated online journal management system or for managing journals manually, via email.

The need for a guide on editorial workflows was identified in meetings of the No-Fee Open Access Publishing in Africa Community of Practice. During discussion it became clear that many different approaches and practices were being used in journal publishing and that some steps in the editorial process were not optimally dealt with. Also, we learned that many journals are using [Open Journal Systems \(OJS\)](#), but only for article publishing, while they manage other stages of the editorial workflow manually.

The guide focuses on editorial procedures rather than editorial roles, taking into account the realities of small editorial teams and reliance on volunteer work. The guide is divided into sections, each covering a different stage in the editorial workflow, from manuscript submission, through editorial review, selection of reviewers, peer review, production, publication and post-publication discussions.

The guide uses screenshots illustrating different editorial procedures in OJS 3.5 (the latest version of the software available at a time of writing this guide), allowing editors to quickly grasp the interface layout and the editorial workflow in OJS.

This guide has two annexes: [Annex 1](#) outlines the essential roles and responsibilities required to manage and publish a Diamond OA journal. For journals that use OJS, we show the wealth of useful email templates that OJS provides for different procedures in the editorial workflow. We include these in [Annex 2](#). These templates could be of interest to journal staff who use other journal management systems or manage journals via email.

The guide has been developed as part of the [Collaboration for Sustainable Open Access Publishing in Africa project](#), funded by the Wellcome Trust [grant number 228148/Z/23/Z]. The authors would like to thank the members of the No-Fee Open Access Publishing in Africa Community of Practice, which was established within the framework of this project, for their valuable input and feedback.

Cite as: Kuchma, I., Smith, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2026). Editorial Workflows in Diamond Open Access Journals: A Guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19569991>

Table of contents

MANUSCRIPT SUBMISSION	3
EDITORIAL SCREENING	13
SELECTING REVIEWERS	16
PEER REVIEW	22
PRODUCTION	27
PUBLICATION	30
INDEXING, ARCHIVING AND DIGITAL PRESERVATION	32
MARKETING AND PROMOTION	33
POST-PUBLICATION DISCUSSIONS	35
Annex I: Roles and responsibilities	38
Annex II: Open Journal Systems 3.5 Email Templates	40
References	73

MANUSCRIPT SUBMISSION

Who is in charge

- [Journal manager](#)¹ (to set up a system for manuscript submission. If you are using OJS or another complex online journal management system, the submission system is integrated as one of its core components)
- [Editorial assistant](#) / [Editor](#) (to manage manuscript from submission onwards and correspond with the authors)

Aim

Receive a manuscript and process it using the online journal management system or a manually managed submissions registration system (e.g. a spreadsheet or other system where all actions related to a manuscript, from submission to rejection or acceptance, are tracked; for the purposes of this guide, we will refer to the manual submission registration system as the Article Database).

Actions

1. An author submits a manuscript using an online submission system or by sending a cover letter, the manuscript and any supporting materials as attachments to a journal's specified email address.

Screenshots from OJS 3.5 are included as examples below. In an online submission system, the manuscript, metadata, images, the cover letter, etc. are uploaded to the system in multiple steps. Using an online journal management system reduces manual e-mail exchanges, minimizes the risk of missing files or information, reduces the need for manual metadata entry, and significantly speeds up the editorial and peer review processes.

Make a Submission

Before you begin

Thank you for submitting to *Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning (CrisTal)*. You will be asked to upload files, identify co-authors and provide information such as the title and abstract.

Please read our [Submission Guidelines](#) if you have not done so already. When filling out the forms, provide as many details as possible in order to help our editors evaluate your work.

Once you begin, you can save your submission and come back to it later. You will be able to review and correct any information before you submit.

1

¹ See the descriptions of roles and responsibilities in [Annex 1](#).

2

Title *

Section *

Submissions must be made to one of the journal's sections.

- Editorial
- Reflections
- Special Issue
- Research Articles
- Review Essays
- Book Reviews
- Reflection and Opinion Pieces
- Poems

Research Articles

This section publishes original empirical, theoretical, conceptual, methodological or review-based research articles that make a clear contribution to scholarship on teaching and learning in higher education. Articles must address a clearly defined problem or question, engage relevant literature, explain the methodological or conceptual approach and show the significance of the argument or findings for a wider readership. Article submissions should normally be 6000–8000 words, excluding references and endnotes, in line with the journal's current [author](#)

Submission Checklist *

All submissions must meet the following requirements:

- This submission meets the requirements outlined in the [Author Guidelines](#).
- This submission has not been previously published, nor is it under consideration by another journal. Where this is not the case, an explanation has been provided in the comments to the editor.
- The submission file is in *OpenOffice*, *Microsoft Word* or *RTF* document format.
- All references have been checked for accuracy and completeness.
- Where available, URLs for references have been provided.
- All tables and figures have been numbered and labelled.
- Permission has been obtained to publish all photographs, datasets and other third-party material included with this submission.
- The text is single-spaced, uses a 12-point font and uses italics rather than underlining, except for URL addresses.
- All illustrations, figures and tables are placed within the text at the appropriate points, rather than at the end.
- Authors have disclosed in their manuscript any use of AI or AI-assisted technologies in the writing process. Authors remain ultimately responsible and accountable for the content of the work. Please see the [Ethics](#) section on the journal site for an example of such a statement.
- All efforts were made to ensure a [blind peer review](#).
- Affiliation names and [ORCID](#)s for authors have been included in the metadata of the submission.

Yes, my submission meets all of these requirements.

Privacy Consent *

Yes, I agree to have my data collected and stored according to the [privacy statement](#).

[Begin Submission](#)

OJS submission form

26829 / Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning

Make a Submission: Details [Save for Later](#)

Submitting to the **Research Articles** section. [Change](#)

1 **Details** — 2 Upload Files — 3 Contributors — 4 For the Editors — 5 Reviewer Suggestions — 6 Review

Submission Details

Please provide the following details in order to help our editorial team manage your submission.

Title *

Keywords *

Keywords are typically one- to three-word phrases that are used to indicate the main topics of a submission.

Educational development x Social realism x Critical realism x
Higher education x

Abstract *

B I x² x₂

Changes in higher education systems across the world have led to the identification of practice and research in the field of Educational Development as a means of addressing what are often conceptualised as 'problems'. This paper argues that the field has not always met the expectations imposed upon it because of conditions that constrain the agency of practitioners to produce research that conceptualises problems meaningfully and identifies practices that will address them. To do this, the paper draws on and extends previous work (Shay, 2012; Boughey, 2022), using a framework based on Bhaskar's (1978) critical realism and Archer's (1995, 1996, 2000) social realism.

References *

Enter each reference on a new line so that they can be extracted and recorded separately.

Archer, M. 1995. *Realist Social Theory: The Morphogenetic Approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
Archer, M. 1996. *Culture and Agency: The Place of Culture in Social Theory*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
Archer, M. 2000. *Being Human: The Problem of Agency*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
Archer, M. 2007. *Making Our Way through the World*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
Barrow, M. & Grant, B. 2011. The 'truth' of academic development: How did it get to be about 'teaching and learning'? *Higher Education Research & Development*, 31(4): 465–477.

Last saved 7 seconds ago

Cancel

Save for Later

Continue

The Author enters all required metadata as part of the OJS submission workflow.

2. File compliance is checked to confirm that all required files (e.g. a cover letter, manuscript, images, etc.) are submitted and that file formats are adequate.

Where submissions are received via email, an initial check is done as soon as the email is received.

If an online journal management system is used, file format compliance is done automatically, before the author presses the "Submit" button. Once the manuscript has been submitted, an editorial executive (e.g. a journal manager, editorial assistant or editor) should review the submitted files to ensure that all required materials are present, the images meet the journal's quality standards, and the content is appropriate and free from spam or unsuitable material.

Make a Submission: Upload Files[Save for Later](#)Submitting to the **Research Articles** section. [Change](#)

✓ Details —
 2 Upload Files —
 3 Contributors —
 4 For the Editors —
 5 Reviewer Suggestions —
 6 Review

Upload Files

Provide any files our editorial team may need to evaluate your submission. In addition to the main work, you may wish to submit data sets, conflict of interest statements or other supplementary files if these will be helpful for our editors.

Files[Add File](#)

 3_Boughey_Galley.pdf

[Edit](#)[Remove](#)

▲ What kind of file is this? [Article Text](#) [Other](#)

[Back](#)

Last saved 2 minutes ago

[Cancel](#)[Save for Later](#)[Continue](#)

The Author uploads all required files as part of the OJS submission process. OJS automatically checks file format compliance.

- Metadata compliance is checked to ensure that all required metadata elements are provided and accurate.

In online submission systems, mandatory fields are clearly indicated and authors cannot proceed if any of these fields is left empty. Also, authors are required to review metadata before pressing the “Submit” button. However, this only ensures completeness, not quality or relevance. For this reason, once the submission is finalized, an editorial executive should review the metadata to verify that it is meaningful and appropriate, as automated checks may still allow irrelevant, nonsensical, or spam entries.

Where submissions are received via email, authors are usually not required to provide metadata in a separate document and an editorial executive should review the manuscript and any additional materials as soon as a submission is received to verify that it contains required metadata elements (title, authors, affiliations, abstract, keywords, etc.).

< Add Contributor**Given Name ***

Family Name

Preferred Public Name

Please provide the full name as the author should be identified on the published work. Example: Dr. Alan P. Mwandenga

1

Email *

Country *

Homepage URL

Competing Interests *

Please disclose any competing interests this author may have with the research subject.

B *I* \times^2 \times_2

Bio Statement (e.g., department and rank)

B *I* \times^2 \times_2

Affiliations

Enter the full name of the institution below, avoiding any acronyms. Select the name from the dropdown and click "Add" to include the affiliation in your profile (e.g. "Simon Fraser University").

INSTITUTION	MORE INFORMATION
Type the institution name in English	
<input type="text"/>	

Contributor's role

Author

Translator

Publication Lists

Include this contributor when identifying authors in lists of publications.

Make a Submission: For the Editors

[Save for Later](#)Submitting to the **Research Articles** section. [Change](#)

Details —
 Upload Files —
 Contributors —
 4 For the Editors —
 5 Reviewer Suggestions —
 6 Review

For the Editors

Please provide the following details in order to help our editorial team manage your submission.

When entering metadata, provide entries that you think would be most helpful to the person managing your submission. This information can be changed before publication.

Supporting Agencies

Supporting agencies may indicate the source of research funding or other institutional support that facilitated the research.

Type *

The nature or genre of the main content of the submission. The type is usually "Text", but may also be "Dataset", "Image" or any of the [Dublin Core types](#).

Data Availability Statement

A short statement describing whether or not the author(s) have made their research data available and, if so, where readers may access it.

B	I	x ²	x ₂	🔗

Comments for the Editor

Add any information that you think our editorial staff should know when evaluating your submission.

B	I	x ²	x ₂	🔗

Funders

Please provide information about any institutions which funded the research behind this work. Only funders from the Crossref registry are supported. If you received funding from an institution and you can not find them to add here, please provide that information in the Comments for the Editor field.

Funding data

[Add funder](#)

Funder name	Funder ID	Grant numbers
<i>No funders</i>		

[Back](#)

Last saved 15 minutes ago

[Cancel](#)[Save for Later](#)[Continue](#)*The Author submits additional metadata.*

Make a Submission: Review

Save for Later

Submitting to the **Research Articles** section. [Change](#)

✓ Details — ✓ Upload Files — ✓ Contributors — ✓ For the Editors — ✓ Reviewer Suggestions — 6 Review

Review and Submit

Review the information you have entered before you complete your submission. You can change any of the details displayed here by clicking the edit button at the top of each section.

Once you complete your submission, a member of our editorial team will be assigned to review it. Please ensure the details you have entered here are as accurate as possible.

Details

Edit

Title

Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning

Keywords

Educational development, Social realism, Critical realism, Higher education

Abstract

Changes in higher education systems across the world have led to the identification of practice and research in the field of Educational Development as a means of addressing what are often conceptualised as 'problems'. This paper argues that the field has not always met the expectations imposed upon it because of conditions that constrain the agency of practitioners to produce research that conceptualises problems meaningfully and identifies practices that will address them. To do this, the paper draws on and extends previous work (Shay, 2012; Boughey, 2022), using a framework based on Bhaskar's (1978) critical realism and Archer's (1995, 1996, 2000) social realism.

References

Archer, M. 1995. Realist Social Theory: The Morphogenetic Approach. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

1

Files

Edit

 3_Boughey_Galley.pdf

Article Text

Contributors

Edit

Chrissie Boughey

Author

For the Editors

Edit

Supporting Agencies

None provided

Type

Text

Data Availability Statement

None provided

Comments for the Editor

None

2

Funders			Edit
Funder name	Funder ID	Grant numbers	

Reviewer Suggestions		Edit
No reviewers have been suggested for this submission.		

3

Submit

The submission, **Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning**, will be submitted to **Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning** for editorial review. Are you sure you want to complete this submission?

Submit Cancel ↶

Last saved 1 minute ago Cancel Save for Later Submit

The Author is requested to doublecheck metadata correctness and press “Submit” as the last step in the OJS Submission process.

4. The manuscript is assigned a manuscript identification number.

When the online submission process is automated, the manuscript receives an automatically assigned manuscript number.

If the process is managed manually, the manuscript is registered and assigned an identifier manually in the internal system where submissions are registered (e.g. a spreadsheet). This manuscript number remains the same throughout the manuscript lifecycle, from submission to publication.

26829

Boughey

Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning

● Submission

26829 in the upper left corner is the unique manuscript number automatically assigned by OJS.

5. The author receives an email confirming the submission.

If an online journal management system is used, this email is sent automatically.

Where submissions are received via email, best practice is to acknowledge receipt immediately upon receiving and checking the manuscript for appropriateness.

Submission Acknowledgement

Ina Smith
To: Ina Smith

Dear Prof Boughey,

Thank you for submitting your manuscript titled "Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning" to [Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning \(CrisTal\)](#). Your submission has been successfully received and registered in our editorial system under the reference number **26829**. You can view and track the progress of your submission by logging into your author account at: <https://journals.assaf.org.za/index.php/cristal/login>

Your manuscript will now undergo an initial editorial check to ensure it complies with the journal's [submission guidelines](#) and falls within its [scope](#). We will notify you as soon as a decision has been made regarding the next steps.

If you have any questions, please contact us at cristaljournal@gmail.com.

Kind regards,

A/Prof Daniela Gachago
Managing Editor: [Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning \(CrisTal\)](#)
University of Cape Town, South Africa
Email: cristaljournal@uwc.ac.za

OJS sends an email automatically to the submitting author as soon as the manuscript is successfully submitted.

Notifications (email templates)

Submission confirmation email

Dear [name],

Thank you for submitting your manuscript titled "[Manuscript Title]" to [Journal Name].

[Submission via a journal management system] Your submission has been successfully received and registered in our editorial system under the reference number [Submission ID]. You can view and track the progress of your submission by logging into your author account at: [link to submission dashboard].

[Submission via email] Your submission has been successfully received by the editorial office and registered under the reference number [Submission ID].

Your manuscript will now undergo an initial editorial check to ensure it complies with the journal's submission guidelines and falls within its scope.

We will notify you as soon as a decision has been made regarding the next steps.

If you have any questions, please contact us at [journal email].

Kind regards,
[Name, role affiliation]

Rejection notification (failure to meet technical requirements)

Dear [name],

Thank you for submitting your manuscript titled "[Manuscript Title]" to [Journal Name].

After an initial technical check, we found that your submission is incomplete or does not meet the journal's file and metadata requirements. Specifically, we noted the following issues: [list issues].

To proceed with the review process, please correct these issues and resubmit your manuscript and additional materials.

Once your corrected submission is received, we will confirm receipt and continue with editorial screening.

Kind regards,
[Name, role affiliation]

Issues that may occur during manuscript submission	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The online submission process cannot be completed due to technical issues (poor connectivity, the journal management system is offline, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Authors are notified (e.g. by publishing information on the journal website) about potential technical issues.• An alternative submission method is provided.• Technical support is available and ensures that the system is up and running.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Files missing• Inadequate file formats• Incomplete metadata• Inaccurate metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Set up the journal management system to automate these checks as much as possible (e.g. restrict file types that can be uploaded, do not allow submission if files are missing).• Reject and require resubmission.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A submission is sent via email, though the journal has an online submission system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A request is sent to the author to submit the manuscript via the journal management system.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Confirmation emails are delayed due to technical issues or the unavailability of staff.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Setting up automated submission confirmations for authors in the journal management system.• Setting up automatic email responses for submissions received via email, for example by triggering replies based on keywords in the email subject line.

EDITORIAL SCREENING

Who is in charge

- [Editorial assistant](#)
- [Editor](#)

Aim

Check the submitted manuscript for compliance with the journal's Aims & Scope and submission requirements.

Actions

1. The editorial executive receives an automated email alert when a manuscript is submitted via the online journal management system or a submission is passed manually to the person(s) responsible for editorial screening. For example, the manuscript can be assigned to an Editor/Section Editor to check it and oversee it through the review process, as illustrated in screenshots from OJS 3.5 below.

A new submission needs an editor to be assigned: Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning

Ina Smith
To: Ina Smith

Tue 2026-04-28 20:28

Dear CrISal Journal Manager,

The following submission has been submitted and an editor needs to be assigned.

[Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning](#)
Christie Boughey

Abstract

Changes in higher education systems across the world have led to the identification of practice and research in the field of Educational Development as a means of addressing what are often conceptualised as 'problems'. This paper argues that the field has not always met the expectations imposed upon it because of conditions that constrain the agency of practitioners to produce research that conceptualises problems meaningfully and identifies practices that will address them. To do this, the paper draws on and extends previous work (Shay, 2012; Boughey, 2022), using a framework based on Bhaskar's (1978) critical realism and Archer's (1995, 1996, 2000) social realism.

Please assign an editor who will be responsible for the submission by clicking the title above and assigning an editor under the Participants section.

This is an automated email from [Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning](#).

An automated email to the editorial executive indicating an editor needs to be assigned.

Editorial Assignment

Ina Smith
To: Ina Smith

Tue 2026-04-28 21:02

Dear Prof/Dr/Other Daniela Gachago,

The submission, "Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning," to [Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning \(CrISal\)](#) has been assigned to you to see through the editorial process in your role as Editor/Section Editor.

Submission URL: <https://journals.assaf.org.za/index.php/cristal/dashboard/editorial?workflowSubmissionId=26829>
Username: dgachago

Please proceed as follows:

- **Screen the submission** to check whether it fits the journal's scope, section, quality expectations and author guidelines.
- **Decide whether it should go to peer review** or be declined at the pre-review/desktop review stage.
- **Select and invite reviewers** if the manuscript is suitable for review (minimum 2).
- **Assess reviewer reports** and make or recommend an editorial decision.
- **Communicate with the author** about revisions, decisions and required changes.
- **Ensure editorial quality and integrity**, including checking for ethical issues, conflicts of interest, plagiarism concerns, and compliance with journal policies.

Thank you and kind regards,

The email sent in OJS to an Editor/Section Editor when a manuscript has been assigned. The email contains instructions about what is expected of them.

2. Author(s) identity is checked (e.g. by checking ORCID records, searching academic databases and generalist search engines, checking institutional websites, etc.).
3. Aims & Scope compliance is checked (primarily by reading the cover letter and abstract).
4. The structure of the manuscript is checked.
5. The formatting of the manuscript and references are checked.
6. In case of noncompliance, the decision is desk rejection and it is communicated to the author(s).
7. If the manuscript has passed these checks, a similarity check is performed to ensure that it does not contain plagiarized content.
8. If no plagiarism is detected, the manuscript is sent for review.
9. If plagiarism is suspected, the manuscript is rejected.
10. The rejection is registered in the manuscript registration system (within the journal management system or in a spreadsheet).

The Editor decides to move the manuscript to the Peer Review stage by pressing “Send for Review” (the blue button to the upper right).

Notifications (email templates)

Desk Rejection: manuscript not within journal scope

Dear [name],

Thank you for submitting your manuscript titled “[*Manuscript Title*]” to [*Journal Name*].

After an initial editorial assessment, we regret to inform you that we will not be sending your manuscript for external peer review. The manuscript was carefully considered by the editorial team, but it is outside of the journal’s scope.

This decision does not reflect the scientific value of your work, but rather its suitability for *[Journal Name]*. We encourage you to consider submitting your manuscript to another journal that may be a better fit for its focus and intended audience.

We appreciate your interest in publishing with *[Journal Name]* and thank you for giving us the opportunity to consider your work.

Kind regards,
[Name, role affiliation]

Desk rejection due to formatting issues

Dear [name],

Thank you for your submission to our journal.

After an initial editorial screening, we have determined that the manuscript does not currently meet our formatting and structural requirements, and we are therefore unable to proceed with the review process at this stage.

We kindly invite you to revise the manuscript to align with our submission guidelines and resubmit it for reconsideration. We appreciate your interest in publishing with us and would be pleased to review the manuscript again once the necessary adjustments have been made.

Kind regards,
[Name, role affiliation]

Issues that may occur during editorial screening	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The journal may be less restrictive in rejecting manuscripts that fall outside scope or do not meet basic requirements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Apply the defined screening criteria consistently, regardless of submission volume.• Use outreach actions to attract good submissions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Giving the same importance to content and formatting during screening could lead to the rejection of potentially strong manuscripts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Prioritize scholarly content over formatting. If formatting is the only issue, allow the work to be resubmitted after corrections.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• If submissions are numerous and screening staff is limited, delays may occur.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Accepting manuscripts continuously, rather than within fixed deadlines, helps reduce bottlenecks.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Author identity may not be verified accurately.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Require ORCID iDs at submission wherever possible.• Use multiple verification sources (indexing databases, World Wide Web, institutional websites, etc.).

- Decisions may be influenced by personal preferences, institutional prestige, language, or region.

- The journal does not have a suitable similarity checking tool.

- Adopt screening checklists to ensure consistency.
- Train editorial staff on bias awareness.
- If possible, ensure double-screening by different persons.

- Pay special attention to inconsistent writing style, unusual terminology, formatting, citation patterns or irrelevant references.
- Rely on the expertise of editors and reviewers.

SELECTING REVIEWERS

Who is in charge

- [Editor](#)
- [Section editor](#) (if applicable)
- [Editorial assistant](#) (optional support role)
- [Editorial Board](#) (if defined so by the journal policy; not a typical setup)

Aim

To identify qualified, unbiased peer reviewers who will evaluate the scholarly quality, originality and contribution of the manuscript. Manuscripts submitted to the journal should pass peer review by at least two peer reviewers before they are published. The information about the peer review process is publicly displayed on the journal website.

Actions

1. The manuscript's topic, methodology, and discipline are reviewed to determine the expertise profile of potential reviewers.
2. Potential reviewers are identified using the journal's reviewer database, reference lists, indexing and academic databases and personal networks. If reviewers are selected from the journal's reviewer database, their previous performance (quality of past reviews, timeliness) is considered. In exceptional circumstances, authors' suggestions can be taken into account, but only with caution and proper verification.

3. Potential conflicts of interest are checked (e.g. shared affiliations, co-authorship, recent collaboration).
4. Potential replacement reviewers are identified if initial invitations are declined or unanswered within the set timeframe.
5. Reviewer invitations are sent via the online journal management system or by email, including the deadlines, manuscript abstract or full manuscript and confidentiality terms.

The screenshots below show the process of assigning peer reviewers in OJS 3.5.

Dashboard / Boughey, Conditions constraining the potential of... / Send for Review

Send for Review

This submission is ready to be sent for peer review.

Select Files

Select files that should be sent to the review stage.

Submission Files

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 164614_3_Boughey_Galley.doc	Uploaded by assafspu on 2026-04-28	Article Text	
---	------------------------------------	--------------	--

[Cancel](#) [Record Decision](#)

Sent for Review

The submission, Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning, has been sent to the review stage. The author has been notified, unless you chose to skip that email.

[View Submission Summary](#)

The Editor/Section Editor selects and uploads an anonymized manuscript, and presses “Record Decision” to move to the Peer Review stage. This activity triggers an automated email notifying the author that the manuscript is being sent for review.

26829

Boughey

Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning

● Review (Round 1)

Activity Log Library

Workflow

- Submission
- Review
- Review Round 1**
- Copyediting
- Production

Publication

- Title & Abstract
- Contributors
- Metadata
- References
- JATS XML
- Galley
- Permissions & Disclosure
- Issue
- Funding data

WORKFLOW: REVIEW (ROUND 1)

Current Submission Language: English

Round 1 Status
Waiting for reviewers to be assigned.

Revisions Uploaded
These files have been submitted by the author after revisions were requested. [Upload](#)

NO	FILE NAME	DATE UPLOADED	TYPE
No Items			

Files for Review
These files will be sent to the reviewers to review. [Upload/Select Files](#)

NO	FILE NAME	DATE UPLOADED	TYPE
164653	3_Boughey_Galley.pdf	28-04-2026	Article Text

Reviewers [Add Reviewer](#)

REVIEWER	REVIEWER STATUS	TYPE	ACTIONS
No Items			

Review Discussions [Add discussion](#)

Name	From	Last Reply	Replies	Closed
No Items				

[Request Revisions](#)

[Accept Submission](#)

[Create New Review Round](#)

[Cancel Review Round](#)

[Decline Submission](#)

PARTICIPANTS [Assign](#)

Khulisa Journals
journal editor

After the manuscript is moved to the Peer Review stage, the Editor needs to add reviewers. In OJS, the process is launched by pressing the “Add Reviewer” button (Review Round 1)

Add Reviewer

Submission Author List

Christie Boughey - Rhodes University

Locate a Reviewer [Filters](#)

Khulisa Journals
Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAF)
 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9710-3668>
✓ 0 Never assigned [Select Reviewer](#)

Paul Prinsloo
Department of Business Management, UNISA
✓ 0 Never assigned [Select Reviewer](#)

Maropeng Modiba
University of Johannesburg
✓ 0 Never assigned [Select Reviewer](#)

Devika Naidoo
University of Johannesburg
✓ 0 Never assigned [Select Reviewer](#)

The Editor can search for a suitable Reviewer in the journal's OJS database (see Search box) and then click on Select Reviewer.

Add Reviewer

Selected Reviewer
Paul Prinsloo [Change](#)

Choose a predefined message to use, or fill out the form below.
Review Request

Email to be sent to reviewer

Dear Prof/Dr/Other NAME

On behalf of [Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning \(CrISal\)](#), we would like to invite you to conduct a review of the manuscript titled "Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning". The submission's abstract is inserted below, and we hope that you will consider undertaking this important task for us.

Do not send email to Reviewer.

Review due date must be greater or equal to response due date.

Important Dates

05-05-2026 26-05-2026
Response Due Date Review Due Date

+ Files To Be Reviewed

Review Type

Anonymous Reviewer/Anonymous Author
 Anonymous Reviewer/Disclosed Author
 Open

[Cancel](#) [Add Reviewer](#)

The Editor prepares the email inviting the Reviewer to review and clicks on "Add Reviewer"

Article Review Request

K Khulisa Journals via Khulisa Journals <Journals@assaf.org.za>
To: Ina Smith

Caution: This is an external email and may be malicious. Please take care when clicking links or opening attachments.

Dear Prof/Dr/Other Khulisa Journals

On behalf of [Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning \(CrISal\)](#), we would like to invite you to conduct a review of the manuscript titled "Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning". The submission's abstract is inserted below, and we hope that you will consider undertaking this important task for us.

Please [login](#) to the journal website by 05-05-2026 to indicate whether you will undertake the review or not. Should you agree, please continue with the [review process](#) of the manuscript and record your review and recommendation to the Editor. The manuscript can be accessed at <https://journals.assaf.org.za/index.php/cristal/invitation/accept?id=8736&key=8uj23m>

The review itself is due 26-05-2026.

If you do not have your username and password for the journal's website, you can use this link to reset your password (which will then be emailed to you along with your username): <https://journals.assaf.org.za/index.php/cristal/login/lostPassword>

Thank you for considering this request.

Ina Smith
Academy of Science of South Africa
[Khulisa Journals](#)

The Reviewer will receive an email invitation to conduct a review of the manuscript.

Notifications and templates

Reviewer invitation

Dear [name],

We would like to invite you to review the manuscript entitled "[*Manuscript Title*]", which has been submitted to [*Journal Name*].

Based on your expertise in [briefly indicate field/topic], we believe you would be well suited to assess this work.

Manuscript details:

- Title: [Manuscript Title]
- Article type: [e.g. Research article, Review]
- Abstract:
[Insert abstract or provide a link]

If you agree to review this manuscript, we kindly ask you to submit your report by **[review deadline]**. The review is expected to focus on the quality, originality, clarity, and relevance of the work, in line with the journal's review guidelines.

If you are unable to accept this invitation, we would appreciate it if you could let us know as soon as possible. If appropriate, you may also suggest alternative reviewers.

[If your journal acknowledges reviewers, you can highlight this in the invitation letter] *[Journal Name]* acknowledges reviewers in accordance with the journal's policies [add: e.g. certificates, annual acknowledgements, ORCID/Reviewer Credits integration].

Please confirm your availability, or contact us if you require any further information.

Kind regards,
[Name, role affiliation]

Conflict of Interest Checklist

This checklist is intended to support the identification of potential conflicts of interest between reviewers and authors in a double-anonymized peer review process. The assessment should be based on available metadata, databases, and publicly accessible information (e.g., institutional websites, ORCID, previous publications). If the journal uses single-anonymized peer review, this checklist can be easily adapted into a self-declaration form and shared directly with reviewers to fill out prior to accepting the review assignment.

Do the reviewer and any of the authors share the same current institutional affiliation?

Yes No Unclear

Is there evidence of recent collaboration between the reviewer and any of the authors (e.g., co-authored publications within the last 3–5 years)?

Yes No Unclear

Are the reviewer and any of the authors involved in the same research projects, grants, or formal research networks?

Yes No Unclear

Is there any indication of a current or past supervisory, mentorship, or student–advisor relationship between the reviewer and any of the authors?

Yes No Unclear

Is there publicly available information suggesting a close personal relationship (e.g., family ties) between the reviewer and any of the authors?

Yes No Unclear

Is there evidence of shared financial interests (e.g., joint patents, company affiliations, advisory roles) that could influence objectivity?

Yes No Unclear

Is there any known history of conflict, dispute, or competition between the reviewer and any of the authors that could bias the review?

Yes No Unclear

Are there any other factors that could reasonably be perceived as a conflict of interest?

Yes No Unclear

Based on the above checks, is there a potential conflict of interest?

Yes No Unclear

Issues that may occur when selecting reviewers	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• It is difficult to identify qualified reviewers, particularly for niche or interdisciplinary topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Maintain an internal reviewer database.• Consult with the Editorial Board members.• Engage with research networks, conferences, and scholarly communities to expand the reviewer pool.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Conflicts of interest may go unnoticed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Require reviewers to declare conflicts before accepting the assignment. Develop and use a conflict-of-interest checklist for consistency.• Check institutional affiliations, recent collaborations, and co-authorships of potential reviewers and authors.• Keep record of detected conflicts of interest.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bias in reviewer selection (e.g. institutional, geographic, or gender imbalance)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Track and report to the journal governance the reviewer diversity to ensure equitable representation of regions, languages, genders and other demographic indicators (race, ethnicity) and institutions. Actively recruit contributors from underrepresented contexts, and promote multilingual participation.

PEER REVIEW

Who is in charge

- [Editor](#) (to manage the process)
- [Section Editor](#) (if applicable, to manage the process)
- [Editorial Assistant](#) (to provide technical support)

Aim

To assess the scientific quality of the manuscript

Actions

Scenario 1: Peer review is managed via an online journal management system

1. The manuscript (anonymized in the case of an anonymized review), the reviewer form and instructions are shared with the selected reviewers, and the deadline is set.
2. Reminders are sent automatically to reviewers, e.g. a week before the deadline.

An automated email reminder in OJS 3.5 sent to the Reviewer to complete review.

3. Reviewers prepare review reports and submit them via the online journal management system. The Editorial Assistant receives an automated notification upon submission.

Review Details: Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning

Khulisa Journals Download Review Form

Once this review has been read, press "Confirm" to indicate that the review process may proceed. If the reviewer has submitted their review elsewhere, you may upload the file below and then press "Confirm" to proceed.

Notified: 28-04-2026 19:59

Reviewer Files Search Upload File

164654 3_Boughey_Galley.pdf 28 April 2026

Recommendation
Set or adjust the reviewer recommendation.

Revisions Required

Reviewer rating
Rate the quality of the review provided. This rating is not shared with the reviewer.

No rating
 ★★★★★
 ★★★★☆
 ★★★☆☆
 ★★☆☆☆
 ★☆☆☆☆

Cancel Confirm

The Reviewer conducts the review and uploads the reviewed manuscript to OJS with Track Changes. The Reviewer makes a Recommendation to the Editor, and then presses "Confirm".

4. The Editorial Assistant checks whether the review reports follow the reviewer guidelines. If not, the reviewers will be asked to amend and resubmit their reports.
5. The Editor / Section Editor checks the content of the review reports.
6. If all reviewers suggest rejecting the manuscript, the decision is made by the responsible editorial body and a rejection notification is sent to the authors.

To: ina@assaf.org.za Add CC/BCC

Subject: [Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning] Editor Decision

B I x² x₂ [Attach Files](#) [+ Insert Content](#)

Dear Ina Smith,

Thank you for submitting your work to Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning.

After careful consideration of your submission, Conditions constraining the potential of Educational Development to impact on the transformation of teaching and learning, and the reviewers' comments, we regret to inform you that we are unable to accept it for publication.

We appreciate the opportunity to consider your work. We hope that the reviewers' comments will be useful should you decide to revise the manuscript for submission elsewhere.

Reviewer comments:

Better suitable for a journal focussing on educational policy. Manuscript content falls outside focus and scope of CriSTaL.

Kind regards,

Editor
Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning

[Visit Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning.\(CriSTaL\)](#) | [Contact Us](#)

If all reviews are positive and no changes are required, the decision to accept the article is made by the responsible editorial body and an acceptance notification is sent to the authors.

In case a minor or major revision is required, the Editor adds comments for authors (if needed), sends the review reports to the corresponding author and sets the deadline for providing a response to the reviews.

7. Reminders about the deadline for submitting the revised manuscript are sent to authors automatically e.g. a week before the deadline.
8. When the authors submit the revised manuscript and comments for reviewers, the Editorial Assistant checks whether the submission is complete.
9. The Editor / Section Editor checks the response. In case of minor revision, the Editor / Section Editor may decide not to send the revised manuscript and the response to reviewers, if they see that the authors have addressed the reviewers' comments. In other cases, the revised manuscript and the response are sent to reviewers for checking and a deadline is set.
10. Reminders are sent automatically to the reviewers.
11. Upon receiving review reports, responsible editorial bodies decide to accept or reject the manuscript.
12. The corresponding author is notified of the decision.

Scenario 2: Peer review is managed via e-mail

1. Editorial Assistant creates a folder in the files archive – a place on a local computer and/or in the cloud where all manuscripts, supporting materials and correspondence are stored and preserved – and saves the original submission (all documents included in the submission such as the manuscript, cover letter, any tables and images, etc.). All further versions of the manuscript, additional files, review reports and correspondence are saved in a dedicated folder and named in accordance with the agreed naming convention.
2. The submission is registered in the Article Database. This could be a simple spreadsheet that contains the manuscript identification number, title, authors, submission dates, as well as the information about reviewers, the peer review process and editorial decisions. The Article Database should also contain links to all relevant documents (cover letter, manuscript, additional files, review reports, responses to reviewers and the revised manuscript).
3. The review management process continues as described in Scenario 1, Steps 3-12. All steps are manually recorded in the Article Database and communication is carried out via email.

The Article Database and the files archive must be owned and controlled by the official journal bodies and must be regularly backed up (on a dedicated drive, another computer or cloud service). It is recommended that files be stored in shared folders, as this allows the Editorial team to monitor progress and supports continuity during staff changes. Data protection measures must be in place to ensure confidentiality and personal data protection in the Article Database and files archive .

In case of double-anonymized peer review, the Editorial Assistant makes sure that the names and affiliations of the authors and reviewers, any references in the text that could reveal their identity and any personal information in the file properties are removed. View example recommendations to ensure a fully anonymous review:

<https://journals.assaf.org.za/index.php/cristal/blindreview>

Notifications (email templates)

Rejection

Dear [name],

Thank you for submitting your manuscript “[*Manuscript Title*]” to [*Journal Name*].

Your manuscript has now been evaluated through our peer review process. After careful consideration of the reviewers’ reports and the editorial assessment, we regret to inform you that we are unable to accept your manuscript for publication. All reviewers raised substantial concerns that, taken together, prevent us from proceeding with the manuscript in its current form. The issues identified would require fundamental changes that go beyond the scope of a revision for [*Journal Name*].

The reviewers’ comments are provided below / in attachment.

We do hope that the feedback received will be useful in improving the manuscript and your research.

Thank you for considering [*Journal Name*] as a potential venue for your work.

Kind regards,

[Name, role affiliation]

Revision

Dear [name],

Thank you for submitting your manuscript “[*Manuscript Title*]” (Manuscript ID: [XXX]), to [*Journal Title*].

After careful consideration and peer review, we would like to invite you to revise and resubmit your manuscript. The reviewers have provided comments that we believe will help you improve the quality and clarity of your work. Their reports are included below / attached to this message.

Please address all reviewer and editor comments point by point, indicating how each issue was handled and where changes were made in the revised manuscript. If you choose not to follow a particular suggestion, please provide a clear justification.

Please submit your revised manuscript and response to reviewers by [deadline]. If you require additional time, please contact the editorial office.

We are looking forward to receiving your revised manuscript and continuing the review process.

Kind regards,

[Name, role affiliation]

Acceptance

Dear [name],

We are pleased to inform you that your manuscript “[*Manuscript Title*]” (Manuscript ID: [XXX]), has been accepted for publication in [*Journal Title*] following peer review.

The reviewers and editors consider your work a valuable contribution to the field. Thank you for your careful revisions and for addressing the reviewers’ comments.

Your manuscript will now proceed to the production stage. You will be contacted by the editorial office with further details regarding copyediting, proofs, and publication scheduling. Please ensure that all required files and metadata are complete and accurate.

Thank you for choosing [*Journal Title*] for the dissemination of your research. We are looking forward to publishing your article.

Kind regards,

[Name, role affiliation]

Issues that may occur during peer review	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reviewers may fail to provide timely response 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Send reminders to prompt timely responses. Identify and invite backup reviewers immediately after a delay is detected. Monitor reviewer performance and prioritize reliable reviewers in future assignments. Consider motivating reviewers by providing rewards and incentives (certificates, “points” that can be used during promotion applications, annual acknowledgements, awards, etc.).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A reviewer has provided a low-quality report 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide clear reviewer guidelines and evaluation criteria to standardize expectations. Use structured review forms or checklists to guide reviewers and improve report quality. Perform editorial quality checks to assess the usefulness and completeness of reviews before making decisions. Consider collecting author feedback on the usefulness of reviews. Request clarifications when reports are superficial or unclear. Monitor reviewer performance and prioritize reliable reviewers in future assignments. Identify and invite a backup reviewer. Provide links to training materials for reviewers and offer training sessions.

PRODUCTION

Who is in charge

- [Journal manager](#) (to coordinate production workflows and platform publishing)
- [Editorial assistant](#) (to manage copyediting, layout, and metadata)
- [Copyeditor](#)
- Proofreader
- [Layout Editor](#)
- IT support may be needed, especially if the publishing platform is custom-made and the Editorial assistant does not have access to some features.

Aim

To convert an accepted manuscript into one or more output formats (e.g. HTML, XML, PDF, ePub) that will be available on the journal's online platform.

Actions

- The Editorial assistant adds (manually) the following to the manuscript: submission, revision and acceptance dates, as well as the licence information.
- The manuscript is sent to a copyeditor, who edits grammar, punctuation, and spelling and makes sure that references are aligned with the journal's citation style. In OJS, a copyeditor can be assigned within the system.
- Layout and typesetting are performed to journal style (e.g. XML, PDF/A, HTML, or JATS production). It is recommended to follow the XML-first workflow, where the manuscript content is first converted to XML, which then serves as the source for generating PDF, HTML, and other output formats (e.g. using tools such as the [JATS XML Converter Service](#)) ([Kupreyev et al., 2026](#)). Figures, tables, and supplementary materials are prepared.
- Author proof is generated and sent to the author for final corrections and approval.
- Accessibility and readability audit is performed. Check that the PDF/HTML has proper heading structure and tags, ALT text for images, readable tables, proper contrast and font size, and machine-readable metadata.
- Metadata (authors, affiliations, abstracts, keywords, funding, references, ORCID, Creative Commons licence that a journal uses, etc.) are prepared and checked.
- A Persistent Identifier (PID) is assigned to the article. In online journal management systems, such as OJS, metadata can be automatically deposited in Crossref via a plugin. If a PID is assigned manually, it is crucial to deposit metadata with the PID registration agency (e.g. Crossref, DataCite) without delay.
- PID is added in all output formats (e.g. PDF, HTML, XML, ePub, etc.). Make sure that it is displayed in line with relevant recommendations (e.g. DOIs should be displayed as full URLs ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2025](#))) and is an interactive link that resolves correctly.
- Final check for errors and omissions to ensure the final version of the article is clean and professional, all hyperlinks in articles are active, and that DOI, ORCID iD and other Persistent Identifiers are correct.

NOTE: When production is done within a single online journal management system, such as OJS, the transition from the production to publication stages is seamless and may appear as a single process. When production is done outside the online journal management system or manually, tasks such as metadata publication or PID assignment may fall within the publication stage.

Notifications (email templates)

Author proof notification email: example

Dear [name],

Your manuscript “[Manuscript Title]” (Manuscript ID: [XXXX]) has entered the production stage.

Please find the article proofs attached. We kindly ask you to review them carefully and return any corrections within [X] days. At this stage, only minor typographical and factual corrections can be accommodated.

If we do not receive your response by the deadline, we may proceed with publication to avoid delays.

Thank you for your cooperation.

Kind regards,

[Name, role affiliation]

Issues that may occur at the production stage	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Delays in copyediting, layout, or proof reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Define production timelines and responsibilities; use standardized templates; monitor progress using a tracking system.• Send reminders.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Metadata errors (e.g., author names, affiliations, funding information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Perform final metadata validation checks before publication.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Limited human and financial resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Prioritize elements essential for content functionality and quality (e.g. structured metadata, readable layouts, accessibility).• Use free or low-cost professional resources (e.g. images under an open licence, open-source templates) instead of expensive stock photos or design services.• Use simple and visually clear design templates that can be maintained by any journal staff member.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Articles are not accessible to users with disabilities and do not comply with accessibility standards (e.g. WCAG).	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use accessible templates for PDF/HTML/XML.• Train staff in basic accessibility principles.

PUBLICATION

Who is in charge

- [Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor](#) (to approve final publication)
- [Journal Manager](#) (to manage platform configuration and dissemination)
- [Editorial Assistant](#) (to coordinate publication tasks and support communication and administrative tasks)

Aim

To make the final version of the article publicly available on the journal platform with complete metadata, Persistent Identifiers, and licensing information, and to disseminate it to discovery and preservation services.

Actions

Scenario 1: Production and publication are handled seamlessly within the same online journal management system

1. Create an issue. If the journal follows the continuous publication model, this is usually done at the beginning of the year.
2. Check article details (metadata, links to full text, licences, etc.) and schedule them for publication.
3. The Journal Manager and an Executive Editor review the full issue and articles and sign off on them.
4. Publish the article / issue and check that metadata are correct to ensure they are proper for indexing and discoverability (e.g. by reviewing article landing pages and meta tags ([Metadata, 2025](#))).

Note: If the journal follows a continuous publication model, articles are published individually as soon as they are ready. If the journal is published issue by issue, articles are organized within an issue and published when the issue is complete.

5. Notify the author that the article has been published. OJS has an automated email notification system.

Scenario 2: Publication is handled outside the online journal management system or manually

1. The final version of the article and associated files (e.g. images, supplementary data, graphical abstracts, etc.) are uploaded to the journal website.

2. Publication metadata, including the licensing and copyright information, are finalized and published with the article.
3. If the journal uses an issue-based model, the article is assigned to an issue.
4. Persistent Identifiers (e.g. DOI) are activated. To activate a PID, the publisher must register it, along with the URL and required metadata, with a relevant PID registration agency (e.g. Crossref or Datacite in case of DOIs).
5. Follow Steps 4-5 in Scenario 1.

Notifications (email templates)

Author is notified about publication

Dear [name],

We are pleased to inform you that your article “[Manuscript Title]” (Manuscript ID: [XXXX]) has been published in *[Journal Title]*.

Your article is available at: [DOI link / article URL].

It is published under the [Creative Commons license type].

Thank you for publishing with *[Journal Title]*.

Kind regards,

[Name, role affiliation]

Issues that may occur at the publication stage	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publication is delayed due to technical or staffing issues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define publication timelines and responsibilities and automate publication steps where possible.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metadata or licensing information is missing or incorrect 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Perform metadata validation before publication.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PIDs or other links do not resolve correctly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Test PID resolution and URLs prior to public release.

INDEXING, ARCHIVING AND DIGITAL PRESERVATION

Who is in charge

- [Journal Manager](#) (to oversee indexing, archiving and compliance)
- [Editorial Assistant](#) (to support submissions to indexing services and documentation)
Institution / Publisher (to support legal deposit and preservation arrangements)

Aim

To ensure the long-term preservation via trusted preservation services and discoverability of published content through systematic indexing and dissemination via indexing services.

Actions

1. Submit content for long-term preservation through archiving and preservation services (e.g. [PKP Preservation Network](#), [LOCKSS](#), [Portico](#), national archives).
2. Submitting required copies (digital and/or print) to designated national libraries or archives in line with national legal deposit requirements (if applicable).
3. Verify that preservation mechanisms are active and functioning – e.g. if you are using the OJS plugin that enables deposition of journal content in the PKP Preservation Network, you need to verify that it is enabled and that content is actually deposited in this preservation service).
4. Ensure that metadata is properly exposed via OAI-PMH² and that complete, high-quality metadata is deposited with DOI registration agencies (Crossref, DataCite, etc.).
5. The article is made discoverable via journal interfaces and machine-readable protocols (e.g. OAI-PMH, APIs).
6. Submit the journal to relevant indexing and abstracting services and aggregators (e.g. [DOAJ](#)) and disseminate metadata either automatically (via OAI-PMH or APIs) or through manual submission.
7. Where appropriate, deposit content or metadata in institutional or subject repositories to enhance visibility.

² OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) is a standard protocol that allows external systems, such as indexing services and aggregators, to automatically collect (harvest) metadata from a journal's platform. OAI-PMH is natively supported in platforms such as Open Journal Systems (OJS) and, in most cases, only needs to be properly configured to allow metadata harvesting.

8. Inform authors of their rights to deposit their published articles in institutional or subject repositories, in accordance with the journal's licensing policy.
9. Maintain records of indexing status, archiving arrangements, and preservation services used.
10. Periodically check indexing services to make sure that your content is still there and verify that content is deposited in preservation systems.

Potential issues related to indexing, archiving and digital preservation	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited resources to support the use of a professional digital preservation service. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journals using OJS can use the PKP Preservation Network free of charge. • Consider applying for support via the JASPER (JournAIS are Preserved forevER) project that focuses on Diamond OA journals indexed in the DOAJ. • Deposit journal content in institutional repositories and/or national archives.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor discoverability due to incomplete or inaccurate metadata 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform metadata validation before DOI registration and publication.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited dissemination and visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure metadata exposure via OAI-PMH and that detailed metadata is deposited with DOI registration agencies. • Register the journal with relevant free indexing services and directories (e.g. DOAJ, BASE, CORE).

MARKETING AND PROMOTION

Who is in charge

- [Journal Manager](#) (to oversee marketing strategy and coordination)
- [Editorial Assistant](#) (to manage announcements and dissemination)
- [Editor](#) / [Section Editors](#) (to support outreach and community engagement)
- Institutional Communication Office (if applicable) (to amplify visibility and ensure alignment with institutional channels)

Aim

Ensure the visibility and impact of the journal and its published content by systematically promoting new publications, calls for papers, and community-related activities to relevant audiences.

Actions

1. Once an article or issue has been published, prepare a standard announcement text and disseminate it via the journal website, mailing lists and newsletters. The announcement should provide key information about the article or the issue's content and include a link to the published version. Links to individual articles should use DOI-based links rather than URLs.
2. Prepare concise and engaging posts for dissemination via the journal's and/or publisher's social media channels. Include key information about the article/issue and a direct link to the published content (preferably via DOI). Ensure that social media posts are aligned with the journal's communication style and branding. Tag authors and relevant institutions, if they are present in the used social media channels.
3. Schedule dissemination across channels (website, email, social media) in a coordinated manner.
4. Inform authors, editors, and reviewers of the publication and encourage them to share the article or issue through their professional networks and social media.
5. Disseminate information about calls for papers, editorial developments, or events beyond regular publication announcements.
6. Share announcements through additional channels where relevant (e.g. institutional websites and social media, mailing lists, partner networks), ensuring alignment with the primary message.
7. Identify articles of broader public or policy relevance and prepare e.g. press releases or media briefings to increase visibility beyond the academic community.
8. If the journal has a printed version, distribute printed issues at events, conferences, and institutional meetings to enhance visibility and support archiving.
9. Track engagement indicators (e.g. downloads, views, social media interactions) and adjust dissemination strategies accordingly.

Potential issues related to marketing and promotion

- Inconsistent or irregular communication

Solutions

- Establish a regular communication schedule and assign clear responsibilities.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low engagement in used communication channels • Lack of time for marketing and promotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the quality and relevance of the promotional content • Diversify communication channels • Optimize timing and frequency
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define priorities and focus on them • Prepare short, ready-to-use templates for announcements and social media posts to reduce preparation time. • Collaborate with institutional support services, if available. • Engage students, if applicable.

POST-PUBLICATION DISCUSSIONS

Who is in charge

- [Editor](#) / [Section Editor](#) (to oversee and respond to post-publication matters)
- [Editorial Assistant](#) (to coordinate communications and documentation)
- [Journal Manager](#)

Aim

To provide clear, ethical processes for handling post-publication commentary, concerns, corrections, and other discussions about published articles in a manner that preserves the integrity of the scholarly record.

Actions

The journal should adopt policies and procedures that align with the [Committee on Publication Ethics \(COPE\) Core Practices for post-publication discussions and corrections](#) (*Post-Publication Discussions and Corrections*, 2018).

1. Provide channels for receiving concerns or critique about published articles (e.g. provide a dedicated email address or web form on the journal website).
2. Review concerns promptly and objectively, in accordance with COPE's guidance that journals must have mechanisms for correcting, revising, or retracting articles after publication when necessary.

3. Post formal journal responses such as corrections, editorial notes, expressions of concern, retractions, or author replies, in line with COPE guidelines on post-publication discussions and corrections, on the journal website and platforms dedicated to post-publication discussions such as PubPeer.
4. Document the outcomes of post-publication processes and update the article's publication record accordingly, and ensure readers are informed of changes.

Notifications (email templates)

Acknowledgement of your post-publication concern

Dear [name],

Thank you for contacting the editorial office regarding the article “[Article Title]” ([DOI / Article ID]).

We acknowledge receipt of your comment/concern and will review the matter in accordance with the journal's editorial policies and COPE guidelines. We will inform you of the next steps and any outcomes once the initial assessment has been completed.

If we require additional information, we will contact you.

Kind regards,
[Name, role affiliation]

Notification to the Author: Request for information on post-publication concern

Dear [name],

We wish to inform you that a concern has been raised regarding your article “[Article Title]” ([DOI / Article ID]) published in *[Journal Name]*.

In accordance with the journal's post-publication procedures and COPE guidelines, we invite you to provide any relevant information or clarification to assist with our assessment. Please submit your response by [deadline, e.g., 14 days from this notice].

All information you provide will be treated confidentially and considered carefully before any decisions or formal notices are issued.

Thank you for your cooperation. Please contact us if you have questions or require clarification regarding this process.

Kind regards,
[Name, role affiliation]

Publication update notice

Dear [name],

We are writing to inform you that a decision has been reached regarding a post-publication issue identified for your article “[Article Title]” ([DOI / Article ID]).

Following an editorial assessment, the journal will publish a formal notice ([correction / editorial note / expression of concern / retraction]) to update the scholarly record. The notice will be linked to the original article and clearly indicate the nature of the update.

You will have the opportunity to review the notice before publication, where appropriate. Please contact us if you have any questions or additional information.

Kind regards,
[Name, role affiliation]

Potential issues related to post-publication discussions	Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Unclear post-publication policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Publish on the journal website a transparent post-publication discussions and corrections policy aligned with COPE Core Practices.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Failure to respond to concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Assign clear responsibility and timelines for handling post-publication issues.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Inconsistent handling of corrections (e.g. the journal issues a correction where a retraction would be more appropriate)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Define in advance the standard outcomes of post-publication discussions (correction, expression of concern, retraction) and criteria for each outcome.

Annex I: Roles and responsibilities

Job titles and responsibilities in scholarly publishing vary widely across publishing communities. While commercial publishers often have clearly defined and standardized roles, such standardization is difficult in Diamond OA journals. Most commonly, this is due to limited resources to hire dedicated professionals for every task. As a result, many tasks in Diamond OA journals are carried out by the same individuals, who combine multiple responsibilities. In this guide, we focus only on the minimum set of indispensable roles necessary to operate a journal. Publishers with more resources may expand their teams and introduce additional roles, such as a managing editor or production manager.

Editorial Board

The Editorial Board is a group of experts who provide strategic guidance to the journal. Its members advise on editorial policies, help ensure the quality and relevance of content, identify new themes, seek to expand the pool of authors and reviewers and promote the journal in the scholarly community. Editorial Board members can also be involved in pre-evaluating submissions, recommending reviewers, or writing editorials.

Editor / Editor-in-Chief

The Editor-in-Chief is responsible for the overall editorial vision and academic standards, policies, and strategic direction of the journal. This role shapes thematic directions and identifies emerging research areas, oversees the editorial process (submission evaluation and peer review), ensures the quality and integrity of published content, participates in final decisions on manuscripts, promotes ethical publishing, diversity, and innovation and represents the journal in academic networks, at conferences, etc. The Editor-in-Chief writes the editorial overview for each issue and guides strategic growth through collaborations. In smaller journals, the Editor-in-Chief may also perform operational tasks, such as coordinating reviewers or approving final versions of articles.

Editorial Assistant

The Editorial Assistant supports the editorial team with administrative and operational tasks, whether manually or through an online journal management system, such as registering submissions, sending confirmation emails, coordinating reviewer invitations and reminders, assisting with proof distribution, and helping manage production tasks. In journals with limited staff, this role is crucial for ensuring the functioning of editorial workflows. In some journals, these responsibilities are distributed across multiple roles (e.g. Managing Editor, Associate Editor, Section Editor, Guest Editor ([ASSAf, 2025](#))).

Journal Manager

The Journal Manager is responsible for the technical and administrative management of the journal (configuring and maintaining the online journal management system, managing user accounts, setting up submission workflows, etc.) ([Learning OJS 3.5 for Journal Managers](#)). In some journals, journal managers may have different responsibilities, such as: managing day-to-day editorial workflow and communication, tracking manuscript progress through the submission system, coordinating with editors, authors, reviewers, and publishers, ensuring deadlines are met and processes run efficiently, and maintaining organizational and professional standards ([JSAA Operational Manual, 2025](#)).

Copyeditor

The Copyeditor reviews accepted manuscripts to improve language, grammar, style, clarity, and formatting. They ensure that manuscripts comply with the journal's style guidelines, references are correctly formatted, and content is consistent and readable. Copyeditors may sometimes check factual details and resolve minor inconsistencies in the manuscript.

Layout Editor

The Layout Editor is responsible for typesetting and preparing the manuscript for publication. This includes formatting the manuscript into final publication-ready formats such as PDF, HTML, or XML, and generating proofs for authors. In many journals, this role is outsourced or is performed by Editorial Assistant.

Additional roles

Advisory Board

A journal's Advisory Board provides strategic guidance and expert advice on the journal's development, helps shape its direction, strengthen the academic quality and enhance its visibility and reputation. Advisory Board members are usually senior scholars who provide guidance on policy, scope, and long-term plans of the journal.

Associate Editor

An Associate Editor supports the editorial process by handling assigned manuscripts, coordinating peer review, and providing recommendations to the Editor / Editor-in-Chief based on reviewers' reports and their own assessment.

Section Editor

A Section Editor manages submissions within a specific subject area or section of the journal. They handle the peer review process for manuscripts in their domain, make recommendations to the Editor-in-Chief regarding acceptance or rejection, and ensure that content meets the journal's standards for quality and relevance.

Guest Editor

A Guest Editor is responsible for managing a thematic section or a special issue of a journal. The role includes inviting authors to contribute, assisting with the peer review process (by suggesting a list of possible peer reviewers), and making editorial recommendations in collaboration with the journal's editorial team.

Managing Editor

A Managing Editor oversees the day-to-day editorial operations of a journal, coordinates submission, peer review, and publication processes.

Production Editor

A Production Editor is responsible for managing the transformation of accepted manuscripts into final publication formats. This role oversees copyediting, typesetting, layout, and format preparation, ensures that metadata and persistent identifiers are accurate, and coordinates proofing with authors. A Production Editor may also be responsible for managing files and uploading content to the journal platform. In many journals, these tasks are performed by Editorial Assistants or Journal Managers.

Annex II: Open Journal Systems 3.5 Email Templates

Introduction

This annex includes 63 email templates³ available in Open Journal Systems 3.5 that can support editorial workflows. They are organized by workflow stage. Depending on your workflow, you may not need all of these templates.

The text of the email templates can be edited, translated and adjusted to your needs. Do not delete or change the variables {text in curly brackets} – e.g. {\$submissionTitle} and {\$submissionUrl} – as these will be automatically populated by OJS. To insert a new {variable}, use **Insert Content** from the toolbar in the email template.

You can find templates by going to: *OJS Dashboard >> Workflow >> Emails >> Add and edit templates.*

Templates

Submission

Template name

Submission Saved for Later

An automated email sent to authors when they save their submission to complete later.

Subject

[Journal title] Submission saved for later: {\$submissionTitle}

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", has been saved for later in {\$contextName}.

You may return to the journal website at any time to complete and submit it:

Submission URL: {\$submissionUrl}

Please note that the submission has not yet been submitted to the journal for consideration. It will only enter the editorial workflow once all required information has been completed and the submission has been formally submitted.

Kind regards,

³ Eight OJS email templates that are intended for subscription-based journals are not included in this Annex.

{contextSignature}

Template name

orcidCollectAuthorId

This email is sent to collect the ORCID id's from authors.

Subject

[Journal title] Please connect your ORCID iD to your submission

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

You have been listed as an author on a manuscript submission to {contextName}.

To confirm your authorship and connect your ORCID iD to the submission, please use the link below:

{authorOrcidUrl}

More information about ORCID at {contextName} is available here:

{orcidAboutUrl}

If you have any questions, please contact the journal.

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Template name

orcidRequestAuthorAuthorization

This email is sent to request ORCID record access from authors.

Subject

[Journal title] Please authorize ORCID access for your submission

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

You have been listed as an author on the manuscript submission "{submissionTitle}" to {contextName}.

Please authorize {contextName} to connect your ORCID iD to this submission and, where applicable, to add the published work to your ORCID record after publication.

To do this, please use the official ORCID authorization link below and follow the instructions:

{authorOrcidUrl}

More information about ORCID at {contextName} is available here:

{orcidAboutUrl}

If you have any questions, please contact the journal.

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Template name

New Version Created

This email automatically notifies assigned editors when a new version of the submission is created.

Subject

[Journal title] A new version was created for "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

This is an automated notification to inform you that a new version of the following submission has been created:

"{submissionTitle}"

You can view the submission here:

{submissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Name

Discussion (Submission) >> Discussion (Submission)

This email is sent when a discussion is created or replied to in the submission stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Discussion regarding submission: "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

A discussion message has been created or updated in the submission stage for the following submission to {contextName}:

"{submissionTitle}"

Authors:

{authors}

Submission URL:

{submissionUrl}

Please log in to review the discussion and respond if required.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name

Submission Confirmation

This email is automatically sent to an author when they make a submission. It provides information about tracking the submission through the editorial process and thanks the author for the submission.

Subject

[Journal title] Thank you for your submission to {contextName}

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

Thank you for your submission to {contextName}.

We confirm receipt of your submission, "{submissionTitle}". A member of the editorial team will review it and you will be notified once the next step in the editorial process has been completed.

You can view your submission and track its progress here:

{authorSubmissionUrl}

If you have been logged out, please log in again using your username:

{recipientUsername}

Thank you for considering {contextName} as a venue for your work.

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Template name

Submission Confirmation (Other Authors)

This email is automatically sent to authors named on a submission who are not the submitting author.

Subject

[Journal title] Submission confirmation: "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

You have been listed as a co-author on the following submission to {contextName}:

"{submissionTitle}"

The submitting author has provided the following author details:

{\$authorsWithAffiliation}

If any of these details are incorrect, or if you do not wish to be listed as an author on this submission, please contact the journal as soon as possible.

Thank you for your contribution to this submission.

Kind regards,

{\$contextSignature}

Editorial screening

Template name

Editor Assigned (Auto)

This email is sent to an editor when they are automatically assigned to a submission.

Subject

[Journal title] You have been assigned to a submission in {\$contextName}

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

The following submission has been assigned to you to manage through the editorial process:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Authors:

{\$authors}

Submission URL:

{\$submissionUrl}

Abstract:

{\$submissionAbstract}

Please review the submission and proceed with the appropriate editorial action. This may include screening the submission, assigning reviewers, declining the submission before review, or moving it to the next workflow stage.

Thank you for your assistance.

Kind regards,

{\$contextSignature}

Template name

Discussion (Submission) >> Assign Editor

This email is sent when a discussion is created or replied to in the submission stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Editor assigned to submission: "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

You have been assigned to manage the following submission to {\$contextName}:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Authors:

{\$authors}

Submission URL:

{\$submissionUrl}

Please log in to review the submission and proceed with the appropriate editorial action. This may include checking whether the submission fits the journal's scope and author guidelines, assessing whether it is ready for peer review, assigning reviewers, or making another appropriate editorial decision.

Please also review any existing discussion messages in the submission stage so that you are aware of the current editorial context.

Thank you for your assistance and for your contribution to the journal's editorial process.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name

Submission Needs Editor

This email is sent to journal managers when a new submission is made and no editors are assigned.

Subject

[Journal title] A new submission needs an editor: "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

A new submission has been made to {\$contextName}, but no editor has yet been assigned.

Submission title:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Authors:

{\$authors}

Submission URL:
{ \$submissionUrl }

Abstract:
{ \$submissionAbstract }

Please assign an appropriate editor or section editor to manage this submission.

Kind regards,
{ \$contextSignature }

Template name

Discussion (Review) >> Assign Editor

This email is sent when a discussion is created or replied to in the review stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Editor assigned in review stage: "{ \$submissionTitle }"

Email body text

Dear { \$recipientName },

You have been assigned to assist with the review-stage management of the following submission to { \$contextName }:

"{ \$submissionTitle }"

Authors:
{ \$authors }

Submission URL:
{ \$submissionUrl }

Please log in to review the current status of the submission and proceed with the appropriate next steps. This may include checking reviewer invitations, following up with reviewers, considering completed reviewer reports, and making or recommending an editorial decision in line with the journal's workflow.

Please also review any existing discussion messages in the review stage so that you are aware of the current editorial context.

Thank you for your assistance and for your contribution to the journal's editorial process.

Kind regards,
{ \$signature }

Template name

Submission Declined (Pre-Review)

This email notifies the author that their submission is being declined, before the review stage, because the submission does not meet the requirements for publication in the journal.

Subject

[Journal title] Decision on your submission

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Thank you for submitting your work to {\$contextName}.

After an initial editorial assessment of your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", we regret to inform you that it will not be sent for peer review.

This decision may be based on the journal's scope, editorial priorities, submission requirements, article type, formatting requirements, or the manuscript's readiness for peer review.

We appreciate the opportunity to consider your work and wish you well should you decide to submit it elsewhere.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Reinstate Submission Declined Without Review**

This email notifies the author that a previous decision to decline their submission without review is being reinstated.

Subject

[Journal title] Pre-review decision reversed for your submission

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

The previous decision to decline your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", before peer review has been reversed.

An editor will assess the submission further and determine the next step in the editorial process.

You can view your submission here:

{\$authorSubmissionUrl}

We apologise for any confusion this may have caused.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name

Submission Accepted (Without Review)

This email notifies the author that their submission is being sent directly to the copyediting stage and will not be peer reviewed.

Subject

[Journal title] Your submission has been accepted without peer review

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

I am pleased to inform you that your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", has been accepted without peer review.

This decision has been made because the submission type does not require external peer review, or because the editor has determined that it may proceed directly to copyediting in line with the journal's editorial process.

Your submission will now proceed to copyediting and production.

You can view your submission here:

{\$authorSubmissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Selecting reviewers

Template name

Review Request

This email from the Section Editor to a Reviewer, requests that the reviewer accept or decline the task of reviewing a submission.

Subject

[Journal title] Invitation to review for {\$contextName}

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

I am writing to invite you to review a submission for {\$contextName}.

Submission title:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Abstract:

{\$submissionAbstract}

If you are able to review this submission, the completed review will be due by {\$reviewDueDate}. Please accept or decline this review request by {\$responseDueDate}.

You can accept or decline the request and access the submission here:

{reviewAssignmentUrl}

If you are unable to review this submission, we would appreciate it if you could decline the request as soon as possible so that we may invite another reviewer.

Thank you for considering this request.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name

Review Confirm

This email is automatically sent when a reviewer accepts a review request.

Subject

[Journal title] Review accepted for "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

{reviewerName} has accepted the review assignment for the following submission:

"{submissionTitle}"

Submission ID:

{submissionId}

Authors:

{authorsShort}

Review type:

{reviewMethod}

Review due date:

{reviewDueDate}

You can view the reviewer assignment here:

{submissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Template name

Review Decline

This email is sent by a reviewer when declining a review request.

Subject

[Journal title] Unable to review "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear Editor,

Thank you for inviting me to review the submission "{\$submissionTitle}" for {\$contextName}.

Unfortunately, I am unable to undertake the review at this time.

Thank you for considering me.

Kind regards,

{\$senderName}

Peer review

Template name**Sent to Review**

This email notifies the author that their submission is being sent to the review stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Your submission has been sent for review

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

I am pleased to inform you that your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", has passed the initial editorial screening and has been sent for peer review.

The editor will invite suitably qualified reviewers to assess the submission. Please note that sending a submission for peer review does not guarantee acceptance for publication. A final editorial decision will be made after the review reports and editorial assessment have been considered.

You can view your submission here:

{\$authorSubmissionUrl}

Thank you for submitting your work to {\$contextName}.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Reviewer Register**

This email is sent to a newly registered reviewer to welcome them to the system and provide them with a record of their username and password.

Subject

[Journal title] Registration as reviewer with {\$contextName}

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

In light of your expertise, we have registered you as a reviewer for {\$contextName}.

This does not commit you to reviewing every request. When you are invited to review a submission, you will be able to view the title and abstract before accepting or declining the request.

Your account details are:

Username:

{\$recipientUsername}

Password:

{\$password}

You may log in to update your profile and reviewing interests.

Thank you for your willingness to support the journal.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Review Reminder (Automated)**

This email is automatically sent when a reviewer has not completed their review by the due date.

Subject

[Journal title] Automated reminder: review due for "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

This is an automated reminder from {\$contextName} regarding your review of the following submission:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

The review was due on {\$reviewDueDate}. We would be grateful if you could submit your review as soon as possible.

Please access the review assignment here:

{\$reviewAssignmentUrl}

If you are unable to complete the review, please contact the journal so that the editor can make alternative arrangements.

Kind regards,

{\$contextSignature}

Template name**Review Reminder**

This email is sent by an Editor to remind a reviewer that their review is due.

Subject

[Journal title] Reminder: review due for "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

This is a gentle reminder regarding your review of the submission "{\$submissionTitle}" for {\$contextName}.

The review was due on {\$reviewDueDate}. We would be grateful if you could submit your review as soon as possible.

You can access the review assignment here:

{\$reviewAssignmentUrl}

If you require a short extension, please contact me so that we can update the editorial record.

Thank you again for your time and contribution.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Review Response Overdue (Automated)**

This email is automatically sent when the deadline for a reviewer to respond to a review request passes.

Subject

[Journal title] Automated reminder: please respond to review request

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

This is an automated reminder from {\$contextName} regarding our request for you to review the following submission:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

We have not yet received your response. Please accept or decline the review request as soon as possible using the link below:

{\$reviewAssignmentUrl}

If you are able to review the submission, the completed review will be due by
{reviewDueDate}.

Thank you for considering this request.

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Template name

Review Round Cancelled

This email notifies the author that a review round for their submission has been cancelled.

Subject

[Journal title] Review round cancelled for "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

A review round for your submission, "{submissionTitle}", has been cancelled.

This may occur when a review round has been opened in error or when the editor determines that another workflow action is more appropriate.

You can view your submission here:

{authorSubmissionUrl}

We apologise for any confusion this may have caused.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name

Reviewer Unassign

This email is sent when an editor unassigns a reviewer.

Subject

[Journal title] Review assignment cancelled for "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

We recently invited you to review the submission "{submissionTitle}" for {contextName}.

This review assignment has now been cancelled. No further action is required from you.

We apologise for any inconvenience and hope that we may call on your expertise again in future.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name**Reviewer Reinstate**

This email is sent when a reviewer that was unassigned is reinstated by an editor.

Subject

[Journal title] Review assignment reinstated for "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

We recently cancelled your review assignment for the submission "{\$submissionTitle}" for {\$contextName}. That decision has now been reversed.

If you are still able to assist with the review, please access the review assignment here:

{\$reviewAssignmentUrl}

If you have any questions, please contact the editor.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Discussion (Review) >> Discussion Review**

This email is sent when a discussion is created or replied to in the review stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Discussion in review: "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

A discussion message has been posted or updated in the review stage for the following submission:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Please log in to {\$contextName} to view the discussion and respond if required:

{\$submissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Review Edited/Edited Review Notification**

This email automatically notifies the reviewer when the details of their review assignment have been changed.

Subject

[Journal title] Your review assignment has been updated

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

An editor has updated the details of your review assignment for {\$contextName}.

Submission title:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Review type:

{\$reviewMethod}

Please respond by:

{\$responseDueDate}

Review due date:

{\$reviewDueDate}

You can view the updated review assignment here:

{\$reviewAssignmentUrl}

Please contact the editor if you have any questions.

Kind regards,

{\$contextSignature}

Template name**Resend Review Request to Reviewer**

This email is sent by an editor to a reviewer who has declined a review request, when the editor wishes to resend the request.

Subject

[Journal title] Review request for "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

We recently invited you to review the submission "{\$submissionTitle}" for {\$contextName}, and you declined the request.

I am writing to ask whether you might now be available to review the submission. We would be grateful for your assistance, but we fully understand if this is not possible.

Please accept or decline the request by {\$responseDueDate} using the link below:

{\$reviewAssignmentUrl}

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Review Request Subsequent**

This email from an Editor to a Reviewer, requests that the reviewer accept or decline the task of reviewing.

Subject

[Journal title] Request to review a revised submission

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Thank you for your previous assistance with the review of "{\$submissionTitle}" for {\$contextName}.

The authors have submitted a revised version, and we would be grateful if you would consider reviewing it in this additional round of review.

Abstract:

{\$submissionAbstract}

If you are able to review this revised submission, the review will be due by {\$reviewDueDate}. Please accept or decline the request by {\$responseDueDate}.

You can access the review assignment here:

{\$reviewAssignmentUrl}

Thank you again for your time and expertise.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Revisions Requested**

This email notifies the author of a decision to request revisions during peer review.

Subject

[Journal title] Revisions requested for your submission

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", has now been reviewed.

After considering the reviewers' comments and the editorial assessment, we invite you to submit a revised version of your manuscript.

Please respond carefully to each reviewer comment and indicate how you have addressed the points raised. If you disagree with a comment, please explain your reasoning respectfully in your response to reviewers.

You can upload your revised manuscript and response to reviewers here:

{[\\$authorSubmissionUrl](#)}

If you have been logged out, please log in again using your username:

{[\\$recipientUsername](#)}

Reviewer comments:

{[\\$allReviewerComments](#)}

Kind regards,

{[\\$signature](#)}

Template name

New Review Round Initiated

This email notifies the author that a new round of review is beginning for their submission.

Subject

[Journal title] A new review round has started for your submission

Email body text

Dear {[\\$recipientName](#)},

Your revised submission, "{[\\$submissionTitle](#)", has been sent for a new round of peer review.

You will be notified once the reviewers' feedback and the editor's decision are available.

You can view your submission here:

{[\\$authorSubmissionUrl](#)}

Kind regards,

{[\\$signature](#)}

Template name

Revised Version Notification

This email is automatically sent to the assigned editor when an author uploads a revised version of an article.

Subject

[Journal title] Revised version uploaded for "{[\\$submissionTitle](#)"

Email body text

Dear {[\\$recipientName](#)},

The author has uploaded a revised version of the following submission:

"{[\\$submissionTitle](#)"

Authors:
{authorsShort}

Please log in to review the revised files and determine the next editorial action:

{submissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Template name

Reviewer Commented Notify Editors

This email is automatically sent to assigned editors when the reviewer makes a review recommendation.

Subject

[Journal title] Review completed for "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

A reviewer has completed a review for the following submission:

Submission:
"{submissionTitle}"

Submission ID:
{submissionId}

Authors:
{authorsShort}

Reviewer:
{reviewerName}

Recommendation:
{reviewRecommendation}

Review type:
{reviewMethod}

Please log in to view the reviewer's comments and continue with the editorial process:

{submissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Template name

Notify Reviewers of Decision

This email is sent by an Editor to a Reviewer to notify them that a decision has been made regarding a submission that they reviewed.

Subject

[Journal title] Decision made on a submission you reviewed

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Thank you again for reviewing the submission "{\$submissionTitle}" for {\$contextName}.

We are writing to let you know that an editorial decision has now been made on this submission.

We sincerely appreciate the time and expertise you contributed to the peer review process.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name

Recommendation Made

This message notifies a senior Editor or Section Editor that an editorial recommendation has been made regarding one of their assigned submissions. This message is used when an editor is only allowed to recommend an editorial decision and requires an authorized editor to record editorial decisions. This option can be selected when assigning participants to a submission.

Subject

[Journal title] Editorial recommendation made for "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

An editorial recommendation has been made for the following submission:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Recommendation:
{\$recommendation}

Please log in to review the recommendation and record the final editorial decision:

{\$submissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{\$senderName}

Template name**Submission Declined**

This email notifies the author that their submission has been declined after peer review.

Subject

[Journal title] Decision on your submission

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Thank you for submitting your work to {\$contextName}.

After careful consideration of your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", and the reviewers' comments, we regret to inform you that we are unable to accept it for publication.

We appreciate the opportunity to consider your work. We hope that the reviewers' comments will be useful should you decide to revise the manuscript for submission elsewhere.

Reviewer comments:

{\$allReviewerComments}

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Resubmit for Review**

This email notifies the author of a "revise and resubmit" decision regarding their submission.

Subject

[Journal title] Revise and resubmit decision for your submission

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", has now been reviewed.

After considering the reviewers' comments and the editorial assessment, we are unable to accept the submission in its current form. However, we invite you to revise and resubmit it for further consideration.

Please respond carefully to each reviewer comment and indicate how you have addressed the points raised. If you disagree with a comment, please explain your reasoning respectfully in your response to reviewers.

You can upload your revised manuscript and response to reviewers here:

{\$authorSubmissionUrl}

If you have been logged out, please log in again using your username:

{\$recipientUsername}

Reviewer comments:

{ \$allReviewerComments }

Kind regards,

{ \$signature }

Template name

Submission Accepted

This email notifies the author that their submission has been accepted for publication.

Subject

[Journal title] Your submission has been accepted

Email body text

Dear { \$recipientName },

I am pleased to inform you that your submission, "{ \$submissionTitle }", has been accepted for publication in { \$contextName }.

Congratulations on reaching this stage of the editorial process. Your submission will now proceed to the copyediting and production stages, where it will be prepared for publication.

The editorial or production team will contact you if any further information or action is required.

You can view your submission here:

{ \$authorSubmissionUrl }

Thank you for choosing { \$contextName } as a venue for your work.

Kind regards,

{ \$signature }

Template name

Notify Other Authors

This email is sent to notify authors of a submission who are not assigned as participants that a decision has been made. Usually these are all others except the submitting author.

Subject

[Journal title] Decision recorded for "{ \$submissionTitle }"

Email body text

Dear { \$recipientName },

A decision has been recorded for the following submission to { \$contextName }:

"{ \$submissionTitle }"

You are receiving this message because you are listed as an author on the submission.

Please contact the submitting author or the journal if you require further information.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name

Reinstate Declined Submission

This email notifies the author that a previous decision to decline their submission after peer review is being reverted.

Subject

[Journal title] Decision reversed for your submission

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

The previous decision to decline your submission, "{submissionTitle}", has been reversed.

The submission will continue in the editorial workflow, and you will be notified when a further decision or action is required.

You can view your submission here:

{authorSubmissionUrl}

We apologise for any confusion this may have caused.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name

Review Acknowledgement

This email is sent by an editor to a reviewer to confirm that their review has been received and to thank the reviewer for their contributions.

Subject

[Journal title] Thank you for your review

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

Thank you for completing your review of the submission "{submissionTitle}" for {contextName}.

We appreciate the time, care and expertise you have contributed to the peer review process. Your comments will assist the editor in reaching a decision and will help the author improve the work where appropriate.

We are grateful for your support of {\$contextName}.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Production

Template name

Sent to Production

This email notifies the author that their submission is being sent to the production stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Your submission has moved to production

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", has now moved to the production stage.

During production, the final publication files will be prepared. The editorial or production team may contact you if any further input is required.

You can view your submission here:

{authorSubmissionUrl}

Thank you for your continued cooperation.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name

Discussion (Copyediting) >> Discussion Copyediting

This email is sent when a discussion is created or replied to in the copyediting stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Copyediting request for "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

A discussion message has been posted or updated in the copyediting stage for the following submission:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Please log in to {\$contextName} to view the discussion and respond if required:

{submissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name

Discussion (Copyediting) >> Request Copyedit

This email is sent when a discussion is created or replied to in the copyediting stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Discussion in copyediting: "{submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

I would like to invite you to undertake the copyediting of the following submission for {contextName}:

"{submissionTitle}"

Please follow these steps:

1. Click on the Submission URL below and log in to the journal.
2. Open the submission and download the file available in Step 1 of the Copyediting stage.
3. Consult the journal's copyediting instructions on the journal website.
4. Copyedit the file carefully, adding author queries where needed.
5. Save the copyedited file and upload it to Step 1 of the Copyediting stage.
6. Once the copyediting has been completed, please use the Complete action/email in OJS to notify the editor.

Journal URL:

{contextUrl}

Submission URL:

{submissionUrl}

Username:

{recipientUsername}

If you are unable to undertake the copyediting at this time, or if you have any questions, please let me know.

Thank you for your assistance and for your contribution to the journal.

Kind regards,

{signature}

Template name

Submission Sent Back from Copyediting

This email notifies the author that their submission has been sent back from the copyediting stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Your submission has been sent back to review

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", has been sent back from the copyediting stage to the review stage.

This may occur when further review or editorial assessment is required before the submission can proceed to publication.

You can view your submission here:

{\$authorSubmissionUrl}

We will contact you if any further action is required.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Submission Sent Back to Copyediting**

This email notifies the author that their submission has been sent back to the copyediting stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Your submission has been sent back to copyediting

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Your submission, "{\$submissionTitle}", has been sent back to the copyediting stage.

This may occur when further copyediting or preparation is required before the final production files can be completed.

You can view your submission here:

{\$authorSubmissionUrl}

We will contact you if any further action is required.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Discussion (Production) >> Discussion (Production)**

This email is sent when a discussion is created or replied to in the production stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Discussion in production: "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

A discussion message has been posted or updated in the production stage for the following submission:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Please log in to {\$contextName} to view the discussion and respond if required:

{\$submissionUrl}

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Discussion (Production) >> Assign Editor**

This email is sent when a discussion is created or replied to in the production stage.

Subject

[Journal title] Editor assignment: "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

You have been assigned as editor/section editor for the following submission to {\$contextName}:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Authors:

{\$authors}

Submission URL:

{\$submissionUrl}

Please review the submission and proceed with the appropriate editorial action. This may include checking whether the submission fits the journal's scope and author guidelines, deciding whether it should be sent for peer review, assigning reviewers, or taking another suitable editorial decision.

Thank you for your assistance and for your contribution to the journal's editorial process.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name

**Discussion (Production) >> Galleys Complete
Subject**

[Journal title] Galleys completed for "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

The galleys for the following submission have been completed:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Submission URL:
{\$submissionUrl}

Please review the final publication files and confirm whether they are ready for publication. Kindly check that the files display correctly and that the article metadata, title, author names, affiliations, DOI, abstract, keywords and other publication details are accurate.

Please let us know if any corrections are required.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name

**Discussion (Production) >> Ready for Production
Subject**

[Journal title] Submission ready for production: "{\$submissionTitle}"

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

The following submission is ready to proceed to production:

"{\$submissionTitle}"

Authors:
{\$authors}

Submission URL:
{\$submissionUrl}

The editorial and/or copyediting work has been completed, and the submission can now be prepared for publication. Please proceed with the production tasks, including layout, galley preparation, metadata checks and any final publication checks required by the journal.

Please let the editorial team know if any information or files are missing.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**Editorial Reminder**

An automated email sent to editors with outstanding tasks to complete.

Subject

[Journal title] Outstanding editorial tasks for {\${contextName}}

Email body text

Dear {\${recipientName}},

You currently have outstanding editorial tasks in {\${contextName}}.

Number of assigned submissions:

{\${numberOfSubmissions}}

Outstanding tasks:

{\${outstandingTasks}}

You can view your assigned submissions here:

{\${submissionsUrl}}

If you have any questions about your assignments, please contact {\${contactName}} at {\${contactEmail}}.

Kind regards,

{\${contextSignature}}

Marketing and promotion**Template name****Issue Published Notify**

This email is automatically sent to registered users when the new issue is published.

Subject

[Journal title] New issue published: {\${issueIdentification}} of {\${contextName}}

Email body text

Dear {\${recipientName}},

We are pleased to announce the publication of {\${issueIdentification}} of {\${contextName}}.

We invite you to read and share the new issue with your scholarly and professional networks.

{\${issueToc}}

Thank you to our authors, reviewers, editors and readers for their continued support.

Kind regards,

{\${signature}}

Template name**New Announcement**

This email is sent when a new announcement is created.

Subject

[Journal title] {\$announcementTitle}

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

{\$announcementTitle}

{\$announcementSummary}

Please visit the journal website for the full announcement:

{\$announcementUrl}

Kind regards,

{\$contextSignature}

Template name**Open Access Notify**

This email is sent to registered readers who have requested to receive a notification email when an issue becomes open access.

Subject

[Journal title] {\$issueldentification} of {\$contextName} is now open access

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

We are pleased to inform you that {\$issueldentification} of {\$contextName} is now available as open access.

You can visit the journal website here:

{\$contextUrl}

Thank you for your continued interest in {\$contextName}.

Kind regards,

{\$contextSignature}

Other**Template name**

Validate Email (Journal Registration)

This email is automatically sent to a new user when they register with the journal when the settings require the email address to be validated.

Subject

[Journal title] Validate your account for {\$contextName}

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Thank you for registering with {\$contextName}.

Before you can use your account, please validate your email address by following the link below:

{\$activateUrl}

If you did not create this account, please ignore this email.

Kind regards,

{\$contextSignature}

Template name

Validate Email (Site)

This email is automatically sent to a new user when they register with the site when the settings require the user to authenticate their email.

Subject

[Journal title] Validate your account for {\$siteTitle}

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Thank you for registering with {\$siteTitle}.

Before you can use your account, please validate your email address by following the link below:

{\$activateUrl}

If you did not create this account, please ignore this email.

Kind regards,

{\$siteSignature}

Template name

Password Reset Confirm

This email is sent to a registered user when they indicate that they have forgotten their password or are unable to login. It provides a URL they can follow to reset their password.

Subject

[Journal title] Password reset confirmation

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

We have received a request to reset the password for your account on {\$siteTitle}.

If you did not request a password reset, please ignore this email. Your password will not be changed.

If you would like to reset your password, please use the link below:

{\$passwordResetUrl}

Kind regards,

{\$siteContactName}

Template name [this email might be inactive – editor/journal manager can no longer create users]

User Created

This email is sent to a newly created user when the editorial manager has created the user through the system.

Subject

[Journal title] User account created for {\$contextName}

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

A user account has been created for you in {\$contextName}.

Your account details are:

Username:

{\$recipientUsername}

Password:

{\$password}

Please log in and update your profile when convenient.

If you have any questions, please contact the journal.

Kind regards,

{\$signature}

Template name**User Invited to Role Notification**

This email is sent to users that are invited to obtain certain roles.

Subject

[Journal title] You are invited to new roles

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

You have been invited by {\$inviterName} to take on one or more roles at {\$contextName}.

Existing roles:

{\$existingRoles}

Newly assigned roles:

{\$rolesAdded}

Please use one of the links below to respond to this invitation.

Accept invitation:

{\$acceptUrl}

Decline invitation:

{\$declineUrl}

If you have any questions, please contact the journal.

Kind regards,

{\$contextSignature}

Template name**User Role Ended Notification**

The email notification sent to a user when they are removed from a role.

Subject

[Journal title] Your role at {\$contextName} has ended

Email body text

Dear {\$recipientName},

Thank you for your contribution to {\$contextName}.

This message confirms that you have been removed from the following role:

{\$roleRemoved}

Your user account remains active, and any other roles you hold are not affected.

If you have any questions, please contact the journal manager.

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

Template name

User Role Masthead Visibility Update Notification

The email notification is sent to a user when their masthead visibility is updated for a role.

Subject

[Journal title] Your masthead visibility has been updated

Email body text

Dear {recipientName},

Your masthead visibility has been updated for the following role at {contextName}:

{roleNameAndDates}

New masthead setting:

{appearOnMasthead}

If you have any questions about this change, please contact the journal manager.

Kind regards,

{contextSignature}

References

- Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf). (2025). *ASSAf's Code of Best Practice in Scholarly Journal Publishing, Editing and Peer Review*. Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf). <https://doi.org/10.17159/assaf.2025/117>
- JSAA Operational Manual: Editorial Roles and Responsibilities, Operations and Processes, Sustainability, Communication and Professionalisation*. (2025). University of Pretoria. <https://upjournals.up.ac.za/index.php/jsaa/libraryFiles/downloadPublic/86>
- Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2025). *Quality in Diamond Open Access Publishing: Guidelines, policies and templates*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17404838>
- Kupreyev, M., Jertec Musap, L., Withanage, D., Jan, M., & Avanço, K. (2026). *XML Publishing [course]*. European Diamond Capacity Hub Training Platform. <https://training.edch.eu/blocks/vitrina/detail.php?id=29>
- Learning OJS 3.5 for Journal Managers*. (n.d.). PKP Docs. Retrieved April 10, 2026, from <https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/learning-ojs/journal-managers/en/>
- Metadata*. (2025). European Diamond Capacity Hub Training Platform. <https://training.edch.eu/blocks/vitrina/detail.php?id=22>
- Post-publication discussions and corrections*. (2018, November 11). COPE: Committee on Publication Ethics. <https://publicationethics.org/news-opinion/post-publication-discussions-and-corrections>